

Saṅgīta Svāra Bhūṣaṇi – An Overview**Srija N¹, Dr. M Subhasree²**¹Research Scholar, Department of Indian Music, University of Madras ²Assistant Professor,
Department of Indian Music, University of Madras**Abstract:**

Carnatic music plays a vital role in South Indian musical tradition. Over the years, these musical traditions have been documented and preserved in manuscripts, treatises, publications and various texts which details the historical evolution of various musical concepts and musical forms. These have been written in several languages like Tamiz, Telugu, Kannada, Sanskrit, Marathi, Bengali, Dēvanāgarī etc. One such work in Tamiz is ‘Saṅgīta Svāra Bhūṣaṇi’. Saṅgīta Svāra Bhūṣaṇi is one of the earliest publications in Tamiz. This text deals with the practical and theoretical aspects of Carnatic music. This paper intends to give an overview of the text Saṅgīta Svāra Bhūṣaṇi.

Keywords: Sangita Svāra Bhusani, Tamil Publication, Indian Music, Narayana Dasar, Arunacalam Pillai, Abhyasa Gana.

Introduction:

Carnatic music has been passed on to generations through oral and textual traditions. The textual tradition includes publications, manuscripts, treatises and so on in different languages like Tamil, Telugu, Malayalam, Kannada, Sanskrit, Marathi, Bengali, etc. There are publications which handle both practical and theoretical aspects of Carnatic music. These works also help in understanding the development of the notation system. One such Tamiz publication is Saṅgīta Svāra Bhūṣaṇi, authored by Nārāyana Dāsar and Aruṇācalam Piḷḷai in 1905.

Saṅgīta Svāra Bhūṣaṇi begins with the theoretical aspects such as sapta svāra-s, sapta tāḷa cakra diagram, six types of aṅga-s with its symbols and five types of jāti-s with its counts, a table of three speeds which is followed by the practical exercises like saralī varisaigaḷ, mēl sthāyi, jaṅṅai varisaigaḷ, alaṅkāram-s, gītam-s and tāna varṅgaḷ. After Tāna

varṇaṅgaḷ, the authors revisit the theoretical aspects namely twenty-two śruti-s, svarasthāna-s, mēḷa rāga-s, janya rāga-s, timing of rāga-s, tāḷadaśaprāṇa-s and vādyaprakaraṇam.

While the book integrates practical exercises between theoretical aspects, this article shall comprehensively discuss the theoretical concepts first, followed by the practical aspects.

Theoretical Aspects:

The theoretical concepts discussed in the publication include twenty-two śruti-s, sapta svara-s, svarastāna-s, sapta tāḷa-s, jāti-s, aṅga-s, mēḷa rāga-s, janya rāga-s, timings of rāga-s, tāḷaprakaraṇam and vādyaprakaraṇam.

The authors begin the text with the following ślōka:

‘Gītavāditya nṛutyānām trayam saṅgītamucyatē
Tānasyādara vudānatvā saṅgītamiti cēritam’

The above ślōka can be interpreted that saṅgītam is the combination of gītam, vādyam and nṛtyam, which is similar to the definition of saṅgīta given by Śārṅgadēva.¹

The ślōka is followed by a table titled ‘Svaragrāmapatakam’ containing the scheme of twenty-two śruti-s, their names and placements in ṣaḍja grāma, mattiyama grāma and gāndhāra grāma.

Mēḷakarta and Janya rāga-s:

The authors have given the following illustration, indicating the svarasthāna-s (rṣabha, gāndhāra, dhaivata, and nishada) of each melakarta.

¹ Subhadra Chaudhary, Śārṅgadēvakṛta Saṅgītaratnākara, Vol 1, Radha Publications, New Delhi, 2000, v. 1.21, pg 12

மேளகர்த்தா அடங்கி யிருங்கும்
ச க் க ர ம்.

						ரிஷபம்,	கரந்தாரம்	
	1	2	3	4	5	6	ஸு	ஸு
	7	8	9	10	11	12	ஸ	ஸா
	13	14	15	16	17	18	ஸு	அம்
	19	20	21	22	23	24	ச	ஸா
	25	26	27	28	29	30	ச	அம்
	31	32	33	34	35	36	ஷ	அம்
தயிவதம்	ஸு	ஸு	ஸு	ச	ச	ஷ		
ரிஷபம்,	ஸு	கை	கா	கை	கா	கா		

It is mentioned that some scholars have classified raga-s into four types namely Rāgāṅga, Upāṅga, Kriyāṅga & Dēṣāṅga and a brief explanation for the same has been given as follows:

- Rāgāṅga – Sampūrna Mēlakarta
- Upāṅga – Auḍava, Śāḍava janya rāga-s
- Kriyāṅga – Janya rāga-s with vakra svāra-s
- Dēṣāṅga – Combination of two different rāga-s which is also known as bhāṣāṅga rāga-s.

This is followed by the section called "Irāga Vibhōda Candirika", in which the authors have listed the rāga-s with its janya-s into two categories namely suddhamattima rāga-s and pratimattima rāga-s.

For each mēḷakarta, the svarasthāna-s - ṛṣabha, gāndāra, dhaivata, and niṣāda are given in which madhyama svarasthana has not been specified as it is already given under the suddhamattima rāga-s category. For example;

Mēḷakarta number 1. Kanakāṅgi – su – r, su – g, su – d, su – n

Kanakāmbari s r g m p d n d s s n d p m g r g r s

Muktatāmbari s r g m p n s s n d m g r s

Suddhamukāri s r g m p d n s s n d m g r s

- The abbreviations for śuddha ṛṣabha, śuddha gāndāra, śuddha dhaivata and śuddha niṣāda is given as ‘su – r, su – g, su – d, su – n’.
- Mēḷa number 29. Dhīraśaṅkarābaraṇam – ca – r, am – g, ca – d, kā – n which denotes that the raga has catuśruti ṛṣabha, amtara gāndāra, catuśruti dhaivata and kākali niṣāda.

Following each mēḷakarta, two or more janya rāga-s are given along with their ārōhaṇa and avarōhaṇa. Alternative ārōhana-s or avarōhana-s / ārōhana-s and avarōhana-s are given. For example;

- *Alternative ārōhana:* Vēgavāhini rāga, which is the janya of Cakravākam

1 – s m g m p d n s s n d p m g r s

2 – s r g m p d n d s s n d p m g r s

- *Alternative avarōhana:* Nīlāmbari rāga, janya of Harikāmbōji

s r g m p d s 1 – s n p d n p m g r s

s r g m p d s 2 – s n p d n p m r m g s

- *Alternative ārōhana & avarōhana:*

a. Pūrvi rāga, janya rāga of māyāmāḷavagaḷa

1 – s r g m p d n p s s n d p m g r s

2 – s r g m d n d s s n d p m d m g r s

b. Rītigaṭṭa, janya of Naṭabhairavi

1 – s r g r g m n d m p n s s n d m p d m g r s

2 – s r g r g m d n d s s n d m g m p m g r s

While it is noted that the mēḷakarta list given in the work is similar to that mentioned in Sangraha Cudāmani of Govinda, the 39th mēḷakarta is mentioned as Jūvarāḷi instead of Jhālavarāḷi. It is also observed that few of the rāgāṅga rāga-s of Venkaṭamakhi's seventy-two mēḷakarta scheme have been mentioned as Janya rāga-s under these mēḷakarta-s.

The rāgāṅga rāga names that are given as Janya rāga-s in the text are listed below:

Mēḷa	Rāgāṅga rāga-s
1	Kanakāmbari
2	Pēnadyuti
4	Bhānumati
5	Manōrañjani
6	Tanukīrti
10	Naṭābharaṇam
11	Kōkilāravam
22	Śrī
29	Dhīraśaṅkarābharaṇam
32	Rāgacūḍāmaṇi
33	Gaṅgātarāṅgiṇi
38	Jaganmōhanam
40	Nabhōmaṇi
44	Bhavāni
52	Ramāmanōhari
53	Gamakakriya
69	Dhautapañcamam
70	Nāsāmaṇi
72	Rasamañjari

The nomenclature of following rāga-s are slightly different with that of the rāgāṅga rāga-s.

Mēla	Rāgāṅga rāga-s	Names in the text – Janya rāga-s
27	Saurasēna	Sarasānana
48	Jīvantikā	Jīvantini
64	Bhūṣāvaṭi	Bhūṣāvaḷi
67	Santānamañjari	Sōmamañjari
68	Jōti	Jōtiṣmati
71	Kusumākara	Kusumāvaḷi

The following rāga-s have been mentioned without the prefix according to the Kaṭapayādi scheme:

Mēla	Rāgāṅga rāga-s	Names in the text – Janya rāga-s
8	Jantōḍi	Tōḍi
9	Dhunibinnaṣaḍjam	Binnaṣaḍjam
14	Vāṭīvasantabhairavi	Vasantabhairavi
16	Tōyavēgavāhini	Vēgavāhini
18	Jayasuddhamāḷavi	Suddhamāḷavi
20	Nāirītigauḷa	Rītigauḷa
23	Gaurivēḷāvaḷi	Vēḷāvaḷi
28	Harikēdāragauḷa	Kēdāragauḷa
34	Bhōgacāyānāṭa	Cāyānāṭa
45	Sivapantuvarāḷi	Pantuvarāḷi
51	Kāsirāmakriya	Rāmakriya
58	Dēśisimharavam	Simmāravam
65	Śāntakalyāṇi	Kalliyāṇi

The authors provide a list of rāga-s that are required to be sung at specified timings. They are given below:

Sl No	Timings	Rāga-s
1.	3am – 6am	Gavuri, pāṇḍi, dēsākṣi, danyāsi, māruva, mattāli, bhūpāḷa, dēvakkriya, dēvagāndāri
2.	6am – 9am	Bhairavi, rēgupti, Yamuna, mukhāri, sāvuḷi, kuramaji, bilahari, malahari, rāmakriya, kaṇṭāravam
3.	9am – 12 noon	Dēśi, pallādi, sāraṅgā, śrirāgam, mēgarañcāni, nīlāmbāri, matyamāvati, maṅgaḷadēśikā
4.	12noon – 3pm	Kāpi, pūrvi, kalyāṇi, mōgana, gūrjari, Vasanta, śaṅkarābharaṇam
5.	3pm – 6pm	Tōḍi, rāmali, varāli, usēni, māḷavi, Yimdōḷa (Hindōḷa), Savurāṣṭaram, nārāyaṇi, pantuvarāli
6.	6pm – 9pm	Nāṭṭa, lalita, sāvēri, kāmbōdi, bēgaḍa, punnāga, manōhari, vēḷāvaḷi, guṇḍakriya
7.	9pm – 12pm	Bavuḷi, baṅgālā, āhiri, kēdāra, asāvēri, maṅgaḷakaiṣikā
8.	12pm – 3am	Karnāṭaka, suraṭi, mamñcari, jōkili, citravēḷa

The sapta svāra-s, sapta tāḷa-s cakra diagram, table for six aṅga-s with their symbols and counts, five jāti-s and their counts have been given. The names of the tāḷadaśaprāṇa-s are mentioned but brief explanation is given only for eight prāṇa-s namely kālam, mārgam, kriyai, aṅgam, laya, giraham, jāti and prastāram, excluding two prāṇa-s - kaḷai and yati.

Vādyaprakaraṇam:

The authors briefly mention about the four types of instruments:

- Aduyēttama – String instruments such as Vīṇa, ālāpini, kinnari, parivādini.
- Suśīra – Wind instruments such as muraḷi, madugari
- Avasattama – Percussion instruments such as mattaḷam, ḍamarikai, pēri, ṭakka, tandubi
- Ghana – Solid instruments such as Cymbal s, bells.

Practical Aspects:

The practical contents of the work includes Saraḷi varisai-s, mēlsthāyi varisai-s, jaṅṭai varisai-s, dāṭṭu varisai-s, alaṅkāram, gītam-s and tāna varṇam-s.

Saraḷi varisaigaḷ:

This section commences with a table for 1st speed (pratamakāla), 2nd speed (dviṭiyakāla) and 3rd speed (tirutiyakāla) followed by twelve saraḷi varisaigaḷ.

Exercise no	Saraḷi varisaigaḷ
1.	s r g m s r g m s r g m p d n s s n d p s n d p s n d p m g r s
2.	s r g m s r s r s r g m p d n s s n d p s n s n s n d p m g r s
3.	s r g s r g s r s r g m p d n s s n d s n d s n s n d p m g r s
4.	s r g m p , p , s r g m p d n s s n d p m , m , s n d p m g r s
5.	s r g m p , s r s r g m p d n s s n d p m , s n s n d p m g r s
6.	s r g m p m g r s r g m p d n s s n d p m p d n s n d p m g r s
7.	s r g m p m d p s r g m p d n s s n d p m p g m s n d p m g r s
8.	s r g m r g m p s r g m p d n s s n d p n d p m s n d p m g r s
9.	s r g m p , g m p , , , p , , ,

	g m p d n d p m g m p g m g r s
10.	s , n d n , d p d , p m p , , , p , , , g m p d n d p m g m p g m g r s
11.	s r g r g , g m p m p , d p d , m p d p d n d p m p d p m g r s
12.	s r g m p , p , d d p , m m p , d n s , s n d p s n d p m g r s

The fourth and eighth varisai-s are not commonly seen in the current textual references. However, it has been followed in the oral tradition.

Mēl sthāyi varisaigaḷ:

This section of the work gives four mēl sthāyi varisai-s which are commonly practised in present day, whereas the fifth varisai in contemporary practise which raises to tāra sthāyi pañcama has not been documented by the authors.

Jaṅṭai varisaigaḷ:

Among the twelve exercises given in the jaṅṭai varisai, the first eight exercises are similar to the present day practice while the ninth to twelfth exercises have new patterns which has been discussed below;

- The ninth exercise follows the ascending (ārōhana) and descending (avarōhana) structure using a repetitive triple-note pattern while each phrase emphasizes the first note with dhīrgha (elongation).

s , s s r , r r g , g g m , m m | p , p p d , d d | n , n n ś , ś ś ||

ś , ś ś n , n n d , d d p , p p | m , m m g , g g | r , r r s , s s ||

- The tenth exercise also follows the repetitive triple-note pattern with dhīrgha on the first note similar to the previous exercise, while at the same time grouping four svāra-s together resembling the structure of the second jaṅṭai varisai.

s , s s r , r r g , g g m , m m | r , r r g , g g | m , m m p , p p ||

- The eleventh exercise resembles the structure of the first exercise following the ārōhana and avarōhana pattern with a quadruple svāra repetition.

s s s s r r r r g g g g m m m m | p p p p d d d d | n n n n ś ś ś ś ||

ś ś ś ś n n n n d d d d p p p p | m m m m g g g g | r r r r s s s s ||

- The twelfth exercise has a quadruple-note pattern similar to the previous exercise, while at the same time grouping four svāra-s together resembling the structure of the second and tenth jaṅṭai varisai-s.

s s s s r r r r g g g g m m m m | r r r r g g g g | m m m m p p p p ||

Alaṅkāram:

The authors document the sapta tāḷa alaṅkāra-s followed by the twenty-eight alaṅkāra-s covering all the thirty-five tāḷa-s. The symbols of tāḷa aṅga-s and number of akṣara kāla-s are given at the top of each exercise.

Gītam:

The text documents notations of twenty gītam-s in different languages, among which nine gītam-s are still in vogue in the present day's oral tradition. It is noted that five gītam-s are in the language Kannada, fourteen gītam-s are in Sanskrit and one in Maṇipravāḷam (Sanskrit, Marati). The composers of the gītam-s are not mentioned in the text, however some of them are also seen in other early Telugu publications such as Svāra mañjari, Pratamabhyāsa Pustakam, Gāyaka Pārijātam.

The first four gītam-s in the work have been listed below:

Gītam	Rāga	Tāḷa
Śrī gaṇa nātha	Malahari	Rūpakam
Kundagaura	Malahari	Rūpakam
Kereya nīranu	Malahari	Tripuṭa
Padumanāba	Malahari	Tripuṭa

The authorship of the above gītam-s are not given in the publication but, it is inferred from other early publications that these were composed by Purandaradāsa. It is noted that the notations of these gītam-s include only the first stanza.

It is seen that the following six gītam-s have the mudra 'gurumūrti' which could be identified as the compositions of Paiḍāla Gurumūrti Śāstri. This includes two lakṣaṇa gītam-s

in Dhanyāsi and Sahāna rāga-s set to Dhruva and Maṭhya tāla-s respectively. Additionally, a maṇipravāla gītam - Pālaya nāgēśvara in Bilahari rāga set to Maṭhya tāla is a combination of the languages Sanskrit and Marathi.

Mīnākṣi jaya	Śrī rāga	Dhruva
Jayakaruṇā – Lakṣaṇa gīta	Danyāsi	Dhruva
Kamsāsura – Lakṣaṇa gīta	Sahāna	Maṭhya
Bhuvanatraya	Kāmbōji	Dhruva
Pāhi śrīrāma	Ānandabhairavi	Dhruva
Pālaya nāgēśvara	Bilahari	Maṭhya

The following two gītam-s which have been identified to be composed by Subbarāma Dīkṣita as documented in Saṅgīta Sampradāya Pradarśini are also seen in this publication.

Gōvinda gōkula	Nāṭṭai	Dhruva
Ārēyānaka	Nāṭṭai	Dhruva rūpaka

The following are the other gītam-s whose authorship could not be identified.

Ānalēkara	Suddha Sāvēri	Tripuṭa
Sakalāsura	Gauḷai	Rūpakam
Rērē śrīrāma	Ārabhi	Tripuṭa
Dhīrutūjāru	Bauḷi	Dhruva rūpaka
Śrī rāmacandira	Bhairavi	Dhruva
Ārere dasarata	Tōḍi	Dhruva
Kamalajādaḷa	Kalyāṇi	Tripuṭa
Ārere virodi	Rītigauḷai	Tripuṭa

Tāna Varṇaṅgaḷ:

Thirteen tāna varṇam-s are seen in Saṅgīta svāra bhūṣaṇi among which ten are set to Ādi tāla and three are set to Aṭa tāla. Similar to the gītam-s, the composers of the tāna varṇam-s have also not been mentioned in the text. However, composer's name were inferred from the other publications like Varṇa Mañjari and Gānāmṛta Varṇa Mālik for a few of them.

The work documents four varṇam-s of Vīna kuppayya. Among them, two are Ādi tāḷa varṇam-s and two are aṭa tāḷa varṇam-s.

Varṇam	Rāga	Tāḷa
Sāmininnē	Śaṅkarābaraṇam	Ādi
Intacāla	Piyākaḍa (Bēgaḍa)	Ādi
Nenaruñci	Danniyāsi	Aṭa
Iḍujākujēsēti	Śrī rāga	Aṭa

Two Ādi tāḷa varṇam-s of Rāmanāḍ Srīnivāsa Iyeṅgār are given:

Varṇam	Rāga	Tāḷa
Vanajākṣi	Kalyāṇi	Ādi
Vanitaninnē	Bhairavi	Ādi

Two Ādi tāḷa varṇam-s of Tiruvotṛiyūr Tyāgayya are given:

Varṇam	Rāga	Tāḷa
Celimikōri	Gauḷa	Ādi
Intamōḍisēya	Sāraṅga	Ādi

The other Varṇam-s are listed below:

Varṇam	Rāga	Tāḷa	Composer
Jalajākṣā	Hamsadhvani	Ādi	Mānambuccāvaḍi Veṅkaṭasubba Iyer
Sarasijumukirō	Ārabhi	Ādi	Pallavi Duraisvāmi Iyer
Sarasūḍa	Sāvēri	Ādi	Kotthavāsala Veṅkaṭarāma Iyer
Taruṇininnu	Kāmbōdi	Ādi	Fiddle Ponnusāmi

Observations:

1. Notations are given for the gītam-s and varṇam-s. The ending of the āvarta is mentioned by using the symbol ‘||’, but the aṅga markings for tāḷa-s are not mentioned. Vowel extensions are given for the kārvai-s. Sthāyi markings are not

specified in the svara-s. Though the notation system was well developed in 1904 as seen in Saṅgīta Sampradāya Pradarśini, it has not been used in this text.

2. It is noted that the edition referred for the study has a missing page which includes a part of the gītam ‘Ārere dasarata’.
3. While the publication has documented several basic exercises, it is seen that the authors have not mentioned the rāga-s for the same.

References

1. Subhadhra Chaudhary, Śārṅgadēvakṛta Saṅgītaratnākara, Vol 1, Radha Publications, New Delhi, 2000
2. Nārāyaṇa Dāsar & Aruṇācalam Piḷḷai, *Saṅgīta Svāra Bhūṣaṇi*, pub. Jīvakāruṇya vilāsam press, Chennai, 1905.
3. Satyanārāyaṇa R, *Caturdaṇḍi Prakāśika of Vēṅkaṭamakhin Volume 1*, Motilal Banarasidass Publishers Pvt Ltd, 2002.
4. Subbarāma Dīkṣita, *Saṅgīta Sampradāya Pradarśini*, Vidya Vilasini Press, Ettayapuram, 1904.
5. Subbarāma Dīkṣita, *Pratamabhyāsa Pustakam*, Vidya Vilasini Press, Ettayapuram, 1905.
6. Taccūru Śīṅgarācāryulu & Taccūru Aḷaha Śīṅgarācāryulu, *Gāyaka Pārijātam*, Śrīnikētaṇa Press, Cennapuri, 1877.
7. Taccūru Śīṅgarācāryulu & Taccūru Aḷaha Śīṅgarācāryulu, *Svaramaṅjari*, Sasilekha Press, Madras, 1924.
8. T K Govinda Rao, *Varṇamanjari*, Gānamandir Publications, Madras, 1979.
9. A S Pañcāpakēśa Ayyar, *Gānāmṛta bōdhini*, Ganamrutha Prachuram, Chennai, 1953.
10. A S Pañcāpakēśa Ayyar, *Gānāmṛta Varṇa Mālika*, Gānāmṛta Pracuram, Chennai, 1958.

Thesis:

S. Vijayalakshmi, *The Evolution, Structure and Musical Analysis of Select Lakṣya and Lakṣaṇa Gīta-s*, University of Madras, 2016.